

CHINA HORIZONS

DEALING WITH A RESURGENT CHINA

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Not all happy: Voices of social critique in contemporary Chinese culture

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Key findings

- Despite tight censorship and ubiquitous practice of self-censorship, there is still space in the Chinese cultural sector for social critique, and there are still artists and writers who decide to tackle important social issues in their works.
- Artists and writers employ various techniques and strategies to voice social critique and avoid negative consequences. These techniques include indirect communication (through the extended use of metaphors, allegories and allusions), using silence and emptiness to convey meaning, focusing on topics which seem non-representative of China as a whole, adorning their critique with didactic postscripts, choosing the genre of comedy to communicate social critique.
- Chinese artists explore topics of social interest falling into three main categories: social and interpersonal dynamics (marriage, parenting, parent-child relations, relations among social peers); economic and structural pressures (environmental concerns, human cost of China's economic rise, critique of neoliberalism and consumerism, corruption and abuse of power, dilemmas of technological advancement); personal identity and well-being (feminist topics, disillusionment, loneliness, personal traumas).
- Social topics undertaken by Chinese artists and writers show both local specificity (e.g. concerns with corruption and the abuse of power), and global embedding (e.g. environmental concerns, critique of neoliberalism and capitalism).
- Our research shows a society tired with ruthless economic growth, families affected by financial pressures and internal generational conflicts, and young people no longer believing that personal happiness is a reachable goal. Chinese society seems to be at a turning point - leaving the era of hectic economic development and facing new challenges of life in an economically disappointing, tech-enhanced authoritarian state.

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Introduction

We are facing increasing challenges in conducting research on contemporary Chinese society: diminishing access to reliable data and fieldwork permissions, distrust among the interlocutors anxious about unwanted consequences, ideological mobilisation and nationalistic feelings preventing the more critical viewpoints. With a tight censorship system and effective self-censorship, there is less and less content available for evaluation by researchers wishing to understand the problems and challenges that members of the society identify as important in today's China.

The field of arts and literature offers an alternative space for research, one that is still relatively accessible and rich in versatile content.

If direct study of society proves difficult, culture gives an indirect, reflected look at social issues as seen, digested and communicated by the artists and writers to their audiences. This research approach is in no way unique - there is a recent precedent to treating cultural texts as indicators of pivotal socio-political developments. From 2017 to 2019, the German Federal Ministry of Defence funded the Cassandra Project, which aimed at predicting potential civil strife in the Balkans, Algeria, and Azerbaijan through analysis of literary works (Greenfield 2021).

Not all creators are interested in social issues. In fact, in today's China it takes courage, not necessarily a political one, but more and more often also financial to discuss them, and most of those working in the cultural sector prefer to steer away from all trouble. Abstract and public art, novels and TV series about imperial China or Hollywood-type commercial film productions are a way to earn a living without treading on the invisible red lines of what is permitted and what is not seen favourably by the censors. And yet a review of several hundred works of literature, theatre, film and visual arts of the Xi Jinping era spanning the years 2012-2024 conducted for this study shows that topics of social interest are present and that their recurring patterns provide valuable insight into contemporary Chinese society.

Topic mapping

Our research identified a large corpus of artistic and literary works of interest from the last decade, dealing with social issues. Almost a hundred of them were selected for close examination. This revealed a list of recurrent topics which can be grouped into the following topic clusters:

Social and Interpersonal Dynamics

- Generational and Familial Conflicts
- Domestic Violence and Family Issues
- Social Marginalisation and Class Disparities
- Societal Expectations and Materialism

Economic and Structural Pressures

- Urban-Rural Divide
- Healthcare and Social Welfare
- Environmental Concerns and Rural Destruction
- Technological Advancement and Its Impact
- State Control and Censorship

Personal Identity and Well-Being

- Gender Inequality and Feminism
- Youthful Disillusionment and Aimlessness
- Mental Health, Alienation and Trauma

These topics reflect some of the interests of artists and writers working in China now, who in their works focus principally on social issues. **The topic list above is by no means exhaustive, and neither is it free from bias on the side of the researchers.** Some topics and concerns intersect and reappear in different sections. For example, China's youths' prospects are portrayed both as a country-specific social dilemma and as part of wider global issues. Despite these restrictions, however, the topic mapping proposed here goes one step further towards understanding what is deemed important in the social discourse of today's China.

Social and Interpersonal Dynamics

Across various media—be it film, theatre, literature, or visual arts—Chinese artists are uncovering and challenging the intricate layers of family relationships, generational divides, and disillusionment felt by both young and old. One of these perspectives is **parent-child relations**, specifically the generational divides and the examination of family bonds. Numerous works, particularly films, focus on themes of generational clash, or alienation within the family. The topic of parental care and family duty is also explored in works by young visual artists. In theatre **there are topics of family strains, broken families (including “left behind” children), or** high expectations of mothers towards their daughters. Another significant issue examined in theatre is the hardship of **parenting under difficult economic conditions**. This includes the struggles faced by female migrant workers, who are often too exhausted to fight

for their maternity rights. The common denominator for these productions is the interest in showing the hardships of ordinary lives, and how upbringing conditions and economic challenges shape and influence relations within families. This interest can be viewed as a continuation of the long-term focus of Chinese artists on the lives of the underprivileged: rural inhabitants, migrant workers, single parents, and people in health crises.

Themes of **marriage and marital relations** are also tackled, particularly in the works of contemporary female writers and dramatists, who examine the societal expectations and disillusionment within marriages. Marital fatigue, inequality, and emotional coldness are subjects of theatrical works. Films confront the challenges of marriage, family reputation, and domestic violence, presenting the struggles of women within constricting social systems. These works also closely touch upon the topics of gender inequality and feminism.

Relations with classmates and social peers form another interesting theme, with works often reflecting the pressure and competition embedded in early life, bullying on campus, a lack of security embedded in the family environment, or a feeling of detachment.

Economic and Structural Pressures

Environmental concerns have been the focus of visual artists ever since China embarked on the rapid road of development at all costs. Pollution and waste became a central theme for works by numerous artists, who produced objects from discarded materials or showed environmental destruction and high levels of pollution through art. Visual artists have consistently worked throughout the last twenty years to show the critical problem of pollution, and the **costs of rapid industrialisation and urbanisation**.

The human costs of China's economic rise are shown from an insider's perspective in a new phenomenon of "low-stratum literature" (*diceng wenxue*). These are works written by rural migrants and other physical labourers who often focus on **the struggle of millions of Chinese** in search of upward social mobility. These poets and writers witness, experience, and translate into poetry and literature the indignities faced by cleaners, nannies, couriers and other low-paid workers - a hot topic also in Chinese social media.

The stunning extent of urbanisation taking place in China produces a growing disparity between the city and the countryside. These socioeconomic developments bear dire consequences for individuals. Writers focus on such problems as **women trafficking** or rural society's increasing brutality and indifference.

Cinematography is a medium especially suited to providing realistic glimpses of "other lives". Some recent films reveal **desperate attempts at upward social mobility** by those on the fringes of the society. The characters are willing to undertake risky or unconventional paths, such as

smuggling electronic equipment or illegal drug testing, as their only way to change their economic situation.

Chinese theatre creators have shown interest in a **critical evaluation of neoliberalism**, as a global issue, but also a part of the Chinese economic model. They point out to spiritual emptiness, mechanical existence, and dehumanisation in a world ruled by money, as well as to the economy-driven gap between traditional and modern rural life. Some of the works combine critique of capitalist and neoliberal economics with a stern look at socialist and communist ideologies. They take on topics of repetitive and solitary office work, labour exploitation, and human alienation. There are others who search for an alternative path - a shift away from material wealth and **consumerism**, and toward the fulfilment found in small pleasures, challenging societal definitions of happiness and inviting a more introspective approach to life satisfaction.

Topics of **corruption, abuse of power or state control** on various levels of business or governmental organizations are also presented in Chinese films, most notably comedies. The specific areas of interest include real-estate fraud, exploitation in mining regions, intervention of the state in private lives, or such specific issues as the financial inaccessibility of cancer drugs caused by local corruption of business and legal circles. Some of the critique voiced in better-known films of nation-wide distribution ignite social discussion and even directly contribute to policy change.

Technological advancement is an important theme in most recent works in visual arts. The last few years since the Covid-19 pandemic have accelerated artists' interest in AI, both as a tool in the artistic workshop and a topic of analysis. In numerous experimental works done with the support or in partnership with AI authors pose questions on human-machine interaction, the nature of humanity and the place of humans in the world of the future.

Similar topics are undertaken in the fast-growing Chinese sci-fi literature. It is now one of the most popular cultural exports of the PRC, enjoying strong state support. This literature, unsurprisingly, dissects relations between humans and technology, also in the local context, showing the hopelessness of an individual posed against **omnipotent technology**. The dystopian, high-technology-driven future is also explored in theatre, in works depicting a future world where humans are fully instrumentalised or in works experimenting with stimulating human emotions with machine-learning.

Many of these issues are global in nature and as such they reshape lives on a level that goes far beyond the Chinese context.

Works by Chinese artists and writers show that many long-recognized social issues, such as environmental pollution, poverty or corruption are still valid topics of concern in the Chinese society of today. But there are new problems as well: ageing, the use of technological tools of control, and the unknown brought about by the advent of AI.

Personal Identity and Well-Being

The last four years since the outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic have put the individual in focus. The traumas of the incessant lockdowns, loneliness, and uncertainty have made their way into public narratives. Economic slowdown and the worsening of China's relations with the West have added fuel to feelings of anxiety and lack of hope. Chinese social media have been flooded with posts by youth who no longer believe in bright prospects for themselves. Terms such as "lying flat" (*tangping*), "letting it rot" (*bailan*), references to a delusional literary character Kong Yiji and "involution" (*neijuan*) have symbolised this loss of hope and the will to struggle. Another term, *run* due to its phonetic proximity to the English language 'run' (as in 'run away') became a keyword for all those young Chinese who feel that emigrating from the country is the only option.

The feeling of **disillusionment and hopelessness** resonates strongly in the works of young Chinese artists in visual arts and theatre. One of the more strikingly recurrent topics in contemporary stage productions is suicide. The issue is explored from the point of views of social alienation, social oppression-induced despair, and mental anguish.

Loneliness is the second topic clearly marked in works by young artists. Some show the feeling of isolation through hostile and towering city structures, others focus on the alienation and misunderstandings within peer groups or longing for a sibling in single-child families. Interestingly, artists have also made note of the anxieties of China's **ageing population**, such as the unease of elderly parents who witness the reversal of traditional family roles. This portrayal reflects the growing isolation that some older adults feel family relations evolve and shows the complex emotional currents that accompany these changes in contemporary Chinese society.

Art can also have a healing function. This process of **dealing with personal traumas** develops sometimes almost unintentionally during performances which open towards audience participation and experience sharing. Such projects uncover a strong need in Chinese society to work through personal traumas which are sometimes well hidden from family members and friends, but manifest themselves in a safe, welcoming space, among strangers.

Trauma transformed into feminist art is strongly present in theatre and in visual arts, with topics such as societal definitions of masculinity, the often-taboo discussions surrounding male sexuality, and the female body. The feminist approach is also introduced through drawing on historic examples of remarkable women: female physicists or previously unknown artists.

In the post-pandemic world, it is no way unique for Chinese artists to be focussing on personal traumas and to be tackling loneliness and alienation in their works. What makes the Chinese experience different, however, is the concurrence of these themes with that of the loss of hope and motivation caused by economic and political shifts.

Ways of voicing social critique

Many topics of social interest are politically charged and taking them on by artists and writers involves certain risks. The Chinese censorship system is effective in its unique flexibility and localisation. The rules are general and vague. It is up to the organiser of a performance (e.g. theatre festival), publisher (literary work), film producer or gallery owner to interpret them correctly and know what can and cannot be said and shown. In the event of wrong judgment and failure to receive the necessary approval for the event or dissemination of a literary work or film, all responsibility rests firmly on the shoulders of these people and the artists. Final decisions are localised through the Central Propaganda Department and other institutions' local branches, whose interpretation can vary and take into consideration local conditions. Initial approval can be withdrawn at any time, also for books that have already been published, and films that have already started to be screened. Self-censorship by the creators themselves, and "preventive" censorship by producers, event organisers, and publishers becomes the most widespread and the most effective tool of control. No gallery or publishing house wishes to be closed, no theatre festival wishes to be cancelled, and no film producer wants to see a film in which millions of RMB were invested being prevented from distribution and cut away from profit-making.

Artists who decide to continue commenting on the social reality of today's China try to find ways and strategies to do so within the boundaries of what is permitted. Similarly to Eastern Europe in the socialist era, Chinese artists proactively and creatively explore various means of indirect communication with their audiences, using allusions and other subtle means.

In visual arts one of them is a silent protest – through expressing the inability to speak or through showing emptiness in lieu of content unwelcome by the state propaganda. The other is inviting the audience to find something out for themselves – giving very weak hints and refraining from providing explicit explanations. Sometimes the title of the work offers the only suggestion on its political message. In other cases, the message looks all too clear, but the curatorial explication of the work seems oblivious to it.

In literature, two interesting approaches can be noticed, representing strategies preferred by older and younger generation writers. Senior writers in their social critique often resort to fable

or farce. Sometimes, they create intricate and elaborate allegories through which they voice their critique or shift the action to imperial China. Younger writers opt for a more toned-down aesthetic that reflects a “knowing but not speaking” attitude and show a calm distrust toward the official (historical) narratives. Especially worthy of notice is a dynamic group of young authors from China’s Northeast areas known as Dongbei (the North-East), sometimes referred to as “China’s Rust Belt” - an area that in the 1990s experienced massive lay-offs, deindustrialization, and economic decline. Now, its culture (and pop culture) is generating new interest across the country, labelled the “Dongbei Renaissance”. The writers represent the “son generation” – descendants of laid-off workers. Their focus on a largely forgotten period of traumatic transformation can be interpreted, somewhat surprisingly, as a longing for stability and relief from anxiety.

In film, we can identify several basic approaches to how the artists express social critique and avoid censorship at the same time:

a) Explanatory and didactic postscripts

In many movies of different topics and genres, we can find “postscripts” at the very end of the movie explaining how the story relates to Chinese realities and policies. They can be interpreted as safety nets for the creators who in this way justify the critical notes of their works.

b) Marginal spaces

Many of the films tackling social topics (critiques directed at state officials or productions merely showing poverty, lack of social harmony, or crime) are set in spaces somewhat on the margins of Chinese society. In this way, the critique can be seen as non-representative of China as a whole.

c) Film genres

In the past years film directors tried escaping the rigid guidelines of the censorship system by embracing specific film genres, such as thriller or film noir, and slipping social critique into the otherwise genre-typical plots. A more recent trend is using the genre of comedy as a vehicle for subtle social critique. These films often aim for commercial success, but touch upon important social issues.

Chinese theatre embraces metaphor and allegory, and due to its inherent flexibility, production contents are often adjusted to a specific stage, time, and context. While scripts need to go through censorship, theatre directors and their casts retain some freedom as to how a given play is produced on a given stage and on a given day. There are locations where more is permitted, such as festivals away from the capital, and locations where every word pronounced on stage is monitored closely by vigilant officials sitting in the audience.

Theatre creators use their experience to assess how far they can go in their social critique in each particular place, adjusting their performances accordingly.

Conclusion - policy implications

The authors of this document propose a mapping of the most important social topics undertaken by Chinese artists and writers in the last twelve years (2012-2024), dividing the topics into three main categories of:

social and interpersonal dynamics;

economic and structural pressures;

personal identity and well-being.

Many of the topics are global in nature, such as environmental concerns, critique of neoliberalism and capitalism or dilemmas connected with technological advancement. Some are more China-specific. These include the human cost of China's economic rise, concerns with the abuse of power, or disillusionment of youth caused by social pressure, economic slowdown, and traumatic personal experiences.

Observing modern China through this "cultural looking glass" shows a society tired of ruthless economic growth, families torn apart by external financial pressure and internal generational conflicts, and young people no longer believing that personal happiness is a feasible goal to achieve. It shows a society at a certain turning point - leaving the era of hectic economic development and facing new challenges of life in an economically disappointing, tech-enhanced authoritarian state. It also shows a society very much conscious of universal issues, one that is in no way separated from the international discourse and from environmental, technological and mental pressures and problems faced by people across the globe.

Our research shows that despite tight censorship and ubiquitous practice of self-censorship, the Chinese cultural sector is not as tightly controlled as could be assumed.

There is still space for social critique, and there are still artists and writers who decide to tackle important social issues in their works. They constantly search for effective and safe ways to communicate with their audiences, including silence and emptiness to convey meaning, allusion, metaphor and allegory, focusing on topics which seem non-representative of China as a whole or adorning their critique with didactic postscripts. This creativity of working within and around the system makes such social critique possible. Their audiences learn to read subtle, indirect content and to interpret what is not said and what is not shown.

With sociological research in China increasingly difficult, it is essential to keep monitoring the Chinese cultural field for themes and content which reflect the contemporary social discourse among the middle class and the educated elites. Such analyses provide direct access to information on domestic issues and processes occurring in the country, which might not otherwise be known and noticed from the outside.

To provide a fuller picture of Chinese society across the different social strata and backgrounds, such research should be paired with large-scale discourse analysis in Chinese social media.

Ongoing **monitoring of the Chinese cultural field** should be part of EC's External Action Service routine activity. For this to be achieved, funds should be allocated, and personnel should be trained.

We advocate for research on culture to be given a higher priority than is the case today.

It is equally important to maintain communication and cooperation links with Chinese artists and writers, not only to keep our understanding of China up to date, but also to provide them with **more opportunities to link with the outside world** and, faced with mounting economic pressure, to be able to pursue their genuine artistic interests. One modest initiative that seemed to have supported the goal of keeping the communication channels open, was the EU-China International Literary Festival, held by the Delegation of the European Union to China. The event had 7 editions until 2023, but due to logistic problems was not organised in 2024. Such initiatives should be kept, and the activity of the Beijing and Hong Kong EUNIC Clusters should be expanded and better financed. It is also important to underline that EU diplomatic missions in China are unique spaces where artists can show their works without going through the official approval procedure.

References

Greenfield, Nathan (2021). "Project Cassandra – Wars and Rumours of Wars". *University World News*. 15 August 2021.

<https://www.universityworldnews.com/post.php?story=20210810211817523> (Accessed December 2, 2024)

A list of works which form the basis for the discussion presented in this Policy Brief can be found in Research Notes: *Mapping the Social Discourse in Chinese Art and Literature of the Xi Jinping Era* by the same authors. The document includes pinyin and Chinese characters for each artist's name and each title of the work mentioned.

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